

Quasi-static and Impact Fracture Behaviors of CFRPs with Nanoclay-Filled Epoxy Matrix

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SUMMARY

This work investigates the influence of nanoclay on the fracture resistance and mechanical properties of nanocomposites and the corresponding carbon fiber-epoxy hybrid composites. The nanoclay augmented the impact and static fracture toughness, as well as the mechanical properties, such as flexural strength and modulus. The fracture surfaces were examined to identify the pertinent toughening mechanisms involved.

Keywords: Carbon fibre; Epoxy; Nanoclay; Fracture; toughening mechanisms

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber-reinforced composites (CFRPs) are a typical of advance engineering materials that exhibit high strength-weight and modulus-weight ratios and are widely used in aerospace, military, sporting goods and automobile industries. Epoxy resins are a very attractive class of polymer for their high strength and stiffness, high temperature resistance, low volatility, low creep, low shrinkage, good adhesion and excellent processability. However, cured epoxy resins are mostly brittle with a low toughness. Nanoclays have been considered a very attractive reinforcement in epoxy systems. The most common clay used in polymer composites is dioctahedral smectite montmorillonite (MMT). Nanoclay-epoxy nanocomposites have shown a wide array of property improvements at low weight fractions of clay, e.g. increased strength, stiffness and high toughness [1,2], thermal stability [2], reduced moisture and gas permittivity [3-6], and superior flame retardancy [7].

Fiber-reinforced composites, nevertheless, also have unique and complex failure characteristics. Upon impact of even modest energy, CFRPs are likely to suffer complicated internal damage including fiber fracture, fiber shear failure, splitting, delamination, transverse cracking, matrix tensile failure and localized compressive failure. The scenario becomes even severe in the presence of any flaw during manufacturing or later in service, which acts as the stress concentration site.

As a continuation of our previous study on impact damage resistance of organoclay-CFRP hybrid composites [8, 9], this study aims to demonstrate significant improvements of fracture properties of the same material against the static and dynamic loads. The possibility of using composite materials for load bearing applications, where the service temperatures can vary a wide range between -20°C to 80°C , has created a need to understand the behaviors at these temperatures. Comparative studies of test

results obtained of the epoxy resin and CFRP composites with and without the addition of nanoclay are provided. Particular focus has been placed on understanding of the toughening mechanisms affected by nanoclay based on extensive microscopic examinations.

2. EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials and Fabrication of Composite Laminates

The nanocomposite constituents and the fibre and matrix materials used in this study were essentially the same as those employed previously [8, 9]. Unidirectional carbon fibre (T200 supplied by Taiwan electrical insulators) with a unit weight of 200 g/m² was used as the main reinforcement for composite laminates. A diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy (Epon828, supplied by Shell Corp) was mixed with 1,3-phenylenediamine (supplied by Aldrich) hardener at a ratio of 100:14.5 by weight. The organoclay, Nanomer I30P (supplied by Nanocor), is an octadecylamine modified montmorillonite suitable for dispersion into an epoxy resin [3, 9]. The required amount of organoclay was dried over night at 75⁰⁰C in an oven prior to use. The epoxy in a glass beaker was heated at 75⁰⁰C to lower the viscosity and the organoclay was added. The organoclay content was varied between 0, 1, 3 and 5 wt% of the epoxy resin-hardener mixture. Mixing was conducted at a shear rate of 3000 rpm for 1h using a high speed shear mixer (Ross). The mixture was subjected to sonication using an ultrasonicator (Branson 1510) at an ultrahigh frequency for 3 h to further disperse the clay, while maintaining the resin temperature at 75⁰⁰C using a hot water bath. The mixture was degassed in a vacuum oven followed by addition of curing agent. CFRP composite Laminates were prepared by hand lay-up on a steel mould plate similar to our previous study [8, 9]. Necessary precautions were taken to keep fabrics well aligned. The molded laminates were wrapped with bleeders and peel plies within Teflon dam all around, which was cured at 80⁰⁰C for 2 h and at 150⁰⁰C for 8 h, followed by post-cure at 160⁰⁰C for 2 h in a vacuum hot press (Technical Machine Product CORP). The high curing temperature excursions for long durations were aimed to make sure the resin was completely cured. A low pressure of 0.3MPa was applied for the first 10 h to maintain a constant fibre volume fraction and a uniform laminate thickness. The laminates were cooled to room temperature before removal from the hot press.

To measure the mechanical and fracture properties of nanocomposites without carbon fibre reinforcement, nanocomposites were also cast into the flat mold having two matching aluminum plates and a Teflon dam of thickness 3 or 5 mm with an approximately square mould cavity. The mould was preheated at 80⁰⁰C. The nanocomposite was cured at 80⁰⁰C for 2 h, followed by postcure at 150⁰⁰C for 3 h.

2.2 Characterization and Mechanical Testing

The flexural strength and modulus of the nanocomposites and the corresponding CFRP laminates were determined from the three point bending test according to specification, ASTM D790, on a universal testing machine (MTS Sintex 10/D). Rectangular specimens of 70 mm long x 12.7 mm wide x 3.0 mm thick were loaded with a span of 50 mm at a crosshead speed of 1.3 mm/min. Five specimens were tested for each set of conditions.

Quasi-static fracture toughness was measured using the compact tension specimens according to the specification, ASTM Standard D5045. Specimens of 50 mm wide x 48 mm high x 5.0 mm thick with an initial crack of 20mm from the loading point were prepared which satisfied the dimensional requirements for the plane strain fracture condition. For CFRP specimens, as shown in Figure 1, the test was conducted along the fiber direction. Specimens were loaded on a universal testing machine (MTS Sintex 10/D) at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min.

Fig.1. Geometry and dimensions of compact tension and Charpy specimens

Charpy impact tests were performed according to the specification, ASTM D6110, on an impact tester (CEAST) with pendulum energy of 2.7 J and a span of 120 mm. The rectangular specimens had dimensions of 126 mm long x 12.7 mm wide x 3.0 mm thick. A 45° V-sharp notch was made at the center of the impact specimens by a razor notching machine (CEAST) with a notch-tip radius of 0.25 mm. For CFRP specimens, as shown in Figure 1, the test was conducted along the fiber direction. The specimens were tested at different temperatures, including the ambient, 80°C and -20°C. Eight specimens were tested for each set of conditions.

To identify the fracture behavior and toughening mechanisms of the organoclay-epoxy nanocomposites and the corresponding CFRP laminates, single-edge-double-notch four-point bend (SEDN-4PB) tests were conducted [10]. Various microscopy, including the optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM), were used to examine the process zone prior to failure around the subcritically loaded crack tip. Fracture surface morphologies were also examined of the clay-CFRP hybrid composites.

An indication for the change in the fracture surfaces was gained by measuring the average surface roughness R_a of the fracture surfaces. The roughness data were determined by optical surface profiler. Because of the textured topography, at least five scans of 2x2 mm area were taken of each sample at regions A and B (see Fig.5) to fully characterize the surface.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Flexural Properties

Flexural strength and modulus of clay-epoxy nanocomposites and the corresponding CFRP laminates are plotted against nanoclay contents in Fig. 2. The flexure strength and modulus of the nanocomposites were increased by 13% and 21%, respectively, with

3wt% clay content. The modulus showed a further increase at 5wt% clay content, whereas the strength revealed a detrimental effect of clay content beyond 3wt%. Essentially the same trend was noted for the mechanical properties of the CFRP composites modified with nanoclay. Because the mechanical properties of fibre reinforced composites in the fibre direction are dominated by the fibre properties, the increases in flexural strength and modulus were less prominent, i.e. 9% and 7%, respectively, than for the nanocomposites. .

The enhancement in the flexural properties could be attributed to the improved interfacial properties responsible for transfer of stresses and elastic deformation in the presence of clay nanoparticles [11]. The flexural strength of a continuous carbon fiber composite depends mainly on the compressive strength of fibres because failure usually starts at the compressive side as a result of significantly lower strength in compression than in tension [12]. Higher modulus fibres would possess more lateral support, therefore, reducing the tendency for fiber micro-buckling or kinking. By the same token, the presence of nanoclay in the epoxy matrix strengthens and stiffens the surrounding matrix, effectively increasing the compressive strength of the composite. The detrimental effect on strength of clay content higher than 3wt% may arise from the formation of agglomerates. It appears that clay agglomerates are particularly detrimental to the fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion, which has a more significant influence on the composites strength than on modulus according to the comparison of data shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. Flexural properties of (a, b) clay-epoxy nanocomposites, and (c, d) clay-CFRP hybrid composites

3.2 Impact Fracture Toughness

The fracture toughness was measured using both the Charpy impact test and the quasi-static compact tension test, and are shown in Fig. 3. The addition of clay into epoxy appears to be more effective at low contents, reaching the highest impact fracture toughness of nanocomposites at 3wt% clay. At a higher content, the impact toughness consistently decreased. The diminishing improvement in impact toughness at high clay contents is attributed to the higher possibility of forming unwanted agglomerates with a relatively large size, which in turn reduced the energy absorbing efficiency of clay. The nanoclay modified CFRPs followed the general trend of clay nanocomposite with respect to clay content when measured at room temperature. Nevertheless, the impact toughness for given clay content was marginally higher for the former composites than the latter nanocomposites, suggesting extra toughening mechanisms arising from the presence of continuous carbon fibres. The details of failure mechanisms in nanocomposites and CFRP hybrid composites will be discussed in Section 3.5.

The varying temperatures chosen for the Charpy impact test represent the upper and lower extremes of temperatures that the CFRP composite components are often subjected to in practical applications. As expected, the impact fracture toughness of clay-CFRP hybrid composites was higher in the ascending order of -20°C , room temperature and 80°C , regardless of clay content. Many similar results on temperature-dependent impact fracture toughness have been reported previously for particle as well as fibre reinforced composite materials, see for example, [13 and 14]. It is generally true that the fracture toughness of polymers increases when the test temperature rises or the strain rate decreases due to viscoelastic behavior of polymers. In this regard, the temperature-dependent impact fracture toughness of the nanocomposites and the clay-CFRP hybrid composites was dominated by the viscoelastic behavior of epoxy matrix in both materials. The presence of nanoclay did not enhance the impact toughness of the hybrid CFRP laminates significantly when tests were conducted at -20°C . The impact fracture toughness values were even lower than the corresponding values for clay nanocomposite. This is because the overall material behavior was very brittle at such a lower temperature, resulting in a very low sensitivity to clay content.

Fig.3. (a) Charpy impact toughness; and (b) quasi-static fracture toughness of clay-epoxy nanocomposites and clay-CFRP hybrid composites.

3.3 Quasi-static Fracture Toughness

The quasi-static fracture toughness values measured from the compact tension geometry for epoxy-clay nanocomposites and corresponding clay-CFRP composites are presented in Fig. 3b. The results clearly indicate that the incorporation of clay into the epoxy matrix had an enhancing effect over the whole range of clay content. It is interesting to note that unlike the impact fracture toughness, the high clay content of 5wt% did not have a negative effect on quasi-static fracture toughness, although the rate of toughness increase rather slowed above 3wt% clay for both the nanocomposite and hybrid composites. Maximum increases in quasi-static fracture toughness by about 36% and 23% were noted, respectively, both at 5wt% clay. These values were significantly higher than the corresponding impact toughness changes at 5wt% clay. It appears that the quasi-static fracture toughness was less sensitive to clay agglomeration than the impact fracture toughness. The details of toughening mechanisms are discussed in the following sections.

It is worth mentioning that the impact and quasi-static fracture toughness values for the clay-CFRP hybrid composites were always higher than the corresponding toughness values for the clay nanocomposites. This observation indicates that there may be additional toughening mechanisms that carbon fibres contributed to further enhancement in energy absorption upon fracture.

3.4 Fracture Surface Morphologies

The fracture surfaces of clay-epoxy nanocomposites and the corresponding clay-CFRP hybrid composites were examined using SEM and typical photographs are presented in Figs. 4-6. It appears that the neat resin exhibited a typically smooth surface with a homogenous material flow in the form of shear lips, which indicates that the resistance of the material to crack propagation was relatively low, leading to brittle failure. On addition of clay the fracture became rough. The higher was the clay content, the rougher was the fracture surface. The shear lips became smaller in size, irregular in shape, deeper and dense, a reflection of crack propagation becoming more difficult with tortuous path with increasing clay content. At a low fraction of 1wt% clay, a clear indication of crack pinning was noted with a tail behind the particles (Fig. 4).

Fig.4. SEM images of charpy impact fracture surfaces of clay-epoxy nanocomposites

The quasi-static fracture surfaces were examined at two different regions, as indicated in Fig.5. Region A represents the crack initiation site and Region B the fast fracture site. The unfilled samples displayed mirror like and featureless surface representative of brittle fracture in a homogeneous material. The clay nanocomposites showed river-markings around the clay particles, an indication that the cracks took more tortuous paths between the regions of high clay concentration due to toughening mechanisms

such as crack tip pinning and bifurcation. The higher was the clay content, the more prevalent were the river-markings. The river-marking became almost negligible in Region B, where the crack propagation was rapid compared to Region A. Indeed the surface roughness measured from these two regions increased almost linearly against the clay content, in a manner functionally similar to the quasi-static fracture toughness shown in Fig. 3(b). As expected, the surface roughness was always higher for Region A than for Region B, consistent with the SEM observations (Fig. 5).

Fig.5. SEM images of compact tension fracture surfaces of clay-epoxy nanocomposites with varying clay contents showing onset of crack initiation (A) and fast fracture region (B)

The corresponding SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of impact and static fracture CFRP composite specimens are shown in Fig. 6. The neat CFRP samples showed smooth surfaces of homogenous matrix material. The fiber surfaces were very clean and completely deprived of the resin. The clay nanocomposite matrix fracture surfaces between the reinforcing fibres were coarse and rough, evidence of higher energy absorption during fracture. The clay-modified epoxy matrix appeared to be better bonded to the fibers than the neat matrix without clay modification. The enhanced adhesion was ascribed to the polarity match between the respective surfaces, since both fibers and nanoclay were inorganic materials functionalized at the surface with organic molecules [15].

Fig.6. SEM images of impact and quasi-static fracture surfaces of clay-CFRP hybrid composites with different clay contents.

Fig.7. Surface roughness of fracture surfaces plotted as a function of clay content, which was measured using an optical surface profiler.

3.5 Toughening Mechanisms

To further scrutinize the fracture behaviors and toughening mechanisms of the clay-epoxy nanocomposites and the corresponding clay-CFRP hybrid composites, the single-edge-double-notch four-point bend (SEDN-4PB) tests were conducted. The tests aimed at gaining insight into the fracture mechanisms responsible for the augmentation of resistance to quasi-static fracture.

Fig.8 Transmitted light optical micrographs of the arrested cracktip: (a) neat epoxy; and (b) epoxy-clay nanocomposites

Fig.9. TEM micrographs showing microvoids in the clay galleries

Fig.10. TEM micrographs showing arrested cracktip

It can be seen from optical microscope images of an arrested cracktip (Fig. 8) that the neat epoxy showed a smooth surface with straight crack, whereas the nanocomposite contained a relatively wider and rougher crack with a tortuous trajectory. The micro or nanovoids ahead of the cracktip were observed. TEM micrographs (Fig. 9) clearly showed occurrence of these microvoids that nucleate from delamination between the clay tactoids under the applied stress field. The opening patterns of these microvoids resemble the occurrence of cohesive failure which is more or less equivalent to cavitations often found in rubber toughened epoxy systems [16]. The cleavage of clay tactoids or the inter-gallery debonding progressively expanded in the longitudinal and lateral sizes, coalesced with similar debonds in the neighboring cluster; eventually turned into subcritical minor cracks ahead of a major crack (Fig.10 b). This may lead to effective relief of the triaxial stress state around the cracktip, resulting in a change of stress state from plain strain to plain stress. Crack tip bifurcation due to the local variations of clay concentration (Fig. 10c and 11), as well as the cracktip arrest due to the presence of transversely located clay bundles (Fig. 10d) were also effective extra energy absorption mechanisms that operated in the fracture process zone. The orientation of clay platelets appeared to be critical in triggering toughening mechanisms like cracktip deflection and blunting. It can be observed (Fig. 10c) that the crack front moves along the clay particles and gets deflected at around 90° with the change of clay orientation from horizontal to vertical direction. Black thick lines show the orientation of clay platelets. The crack front at an obstacle may diverge from the initial propagation plane by tilting and twisting. Such deflection causes a change in the stress field from pure mode I to mix-mode which requires a higher driving force and results in a higher fracture surface area and toughness [17].

Fig. 11. SEM Micrographs of the arrested cracktip (a) neat epoxy, (b) epoxy-clay nanocomposites

The clay-CFRP hybrid composites were examined after the SEDN-4PB test, so that key toughening mechanisms and the sequence of toughening events can be identified. Apart from the aforementioned mechanisms, some additional mechanisms arising from the presence of fiber were also found. Fig.12 shows SEM micrographs of the sequential failure events. Multilayer delaminations were observed ahead of a propagating crack, much the same manner as the microvoids that were seen at the vicinity of cracks in nanocomposites. The delamination was followed by fiber bridging and further debonding of the fiber matrix interface, and eventually fiber fracture. The presence of clay in the matrix made the matrix material stiffer and the interfacial adhesion stronger, augmenting energy absorption during the fiber pullout process.

Fig.12. SEM micrographs showing sequential failure mechanisms of clay-CFRP hybrid composites.

4. Concluding remarks

The mechanical and fracture properties of clay-epoxy nanocomposite and clay-CFRP hybrid composites were studied. The mechanical properties were evaluated by flexural measurements. The impact fracture toughness was measured by Charpy impact test whereas the quasi-static fracture toughness was measured by compact tension test. The impact fracture toughness was also evaluated at ambient, 80°C and -20°C.

The flexural modulus and strength were enhanced by the addition of clay to the epoxy matrix and corresponding CFRPs. The impact fracture toughness of clay-epoxy nanocomposite and clay-CFRP hybrid composites were increased to a maximum at 3wt% clay and showed a decreasing trend upon further addition of clay. The impact fracture toughness of clay-CFRP hybrid composites was higher in the ascending order of -20°C, room temperature and 80°C, regardless of clay content, showing the dominant viscoelastic behavior of the matrix.

The clay brought about significant improvement in critical stress intensity factor over the whole range of clay content for both clay-epoxy nanocomposite and clay-CFRP hybrid composite. The impact and quasi-static fracture toughness values for the clay-CFRP hybrid composites were higher than the corresponding toughness values for the clay nanocomposites because of additional toughening in the presence of carbon fiber.

Single-edge-double-notch four-point bend (SEDN-4PB) tests were conducted to gain insight into the toughening mechanisms implicated for the enhancement of fracture toughness. Microcracking at the vicinity of cracktip, crack pinning, bifurcation and multilayer delaminations were among key toughening mechanisms identified.

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